

ratio were higher with maize alone, followed by maize at 2.5-m row spacing.

Rice - maize intercropping may be more profitable than rice alone. Further research is needed to select appropriate rice varieties and fertilizer management for the system. □

Performance of oilseed and pulse crops in a rice-based cropping sequence

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Long-duration rice varieties and excess moisture delay sowing of dry season crops in the rainfed lowlands. Oilseeds and pulses are cultivated as relay or sequence crops, but yields are poor because of poor plant stands due to lack of adequate nutrients.

We studied the effect of seed rate and fertilizer on the productivity of a rice-based cropping system 1986-87 to 1988-89, in a randomized block design with four replications.

Economic analysis

Use of bullock power in rice production

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Draft animal power is a critical component of rice-based cropping systems in Tamil Nadu. Rice requires more animal power than other crops because transplanting involves extensive tillage: plowing, puddling, bunding, and leveling. We studied the cost of draft animal power use on rice farms using 1971-72 to 1983-84 data from the scheme on Cost of Cultivation of Principal Crops (CCPC) covering the state's rice belt.

Bullock pair hours/ha fluctuate. Bullock costs/ha have increased (see table). But the proportion of total

Yields and net return^a of rice-based cropping systems in rainfed lowlands. Ghagharaghat, UP, India, 1986-89.^b

Treatment ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)		Cost (\$/ha)	Gross income (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)	Benefit: cost ratio
	Rice	Second crop				
Rice alone	2.4	-	167	338	171	2.02
Rice - lentil + S ₁ F ₁	2.4	0.230	211	372	161	1.76
Rice - lentil + S ₁ F ₂	2.4	0.409	235	472	237	2.01
Rice - lentil + S ₂ F ₁	2.4	0.365	218	391	173	1.79
Rice - lentil + S ₂ F ₂	2.4	0.635	242	546	304	2.25
Rice - linseed + S ₁ F ₁	2.4	0.235	222	442	220	1.99
Rice - linseed + S ₁ F ₂	2.4	0.498	242	541	299	2.23
Rice - linseed + S ₂ F ₁	2.4	0.413	228	506	278	2.21
Rice - linseed + S ₂ F ₂	2.4	0.664	249	608	359	2.44
Rice - mustard + S ₁ F ₁	2.4	0.168	203	416	213	2.04
Rice - mustard + S ₁ F ₂	2.4	0.212	228	438	210	1.91
Rice - mustard + S ₂ F ₁	2.4	0.199	216	430	214	1.99
Rice - mustard + S ₂ F ₂	2.4	0.262	230	459	229	1.99

^a Av of 3 crop years. US\$1 = Rs 16.32. ^b S₁ = normal seed rate (kg/ha): linseed 30, lentil 40, mustard 5; S₂ = 50% extra seed than normal (kg/ha): linseed 45, lentil 60, mustard 7.50; F₁ = without fertilizer, F₂ = recommended fertilizer (pulses: 20 kg N + 17.6 kg P/ha) and (oilseeds: 30 kg N + 8.8 kg P/ha).

The experiment site had sandy to clay loam soil with pH 8.1, 0.38% organic C, 23.8 kg available P₂O₅, and 267 kg K₂O/ha. Rice variety Madhukar was transplanted the third week of Jul at 20- × 15-cm spacing with 40-20-20 kg NPK/ha. Lentil variety PL 406, linseed variety Mukta, and mustard variety Varuna were broadcast in the standing rice crop 8 d before harvest the last week of Nov.

All the dry season crops produced higher grain yields with higher seeding rates and fertilizer (see table). The highest net return was with rice - linseed at higher seeding rate + fertilizer (\$359/ha), followed by rice - lentil at higher seed rate + fertilizer (\$304/ha). Lowest net return was with rice - lentil at normal seeding rate without fertilizer. □

Bullock power use on Tamil Nadu rice farms.

Year	Cost of hired bullock (\$/ha)	Cost of owned bullock (\$/ha)	Total bullock cost (\$/ha)	Total bullock pair use (h/ha)	Total production cost (\$/ha)	Bullock cost: total cost (%)
1971-72	2.67	4.81	7.48	255.29	96.89	7.72
1972-73	(35.70) 2.17	(64.30) 3.51	5.68	283.34	92.36	6.15
1973-74	(38.20) 2.67	(61.80) 4.81	7.48	219.10	72.48	10.32
1974-75	(35.70) 4.41	(64.30) 6.91	11.32	199.77	197.90	5.72
1975-76	(38.96) 3.43	(61.04) 13.29	16.72	224.76	165.71	10.09
1976-77	(20.50) 2.06	(79.50) 17.39	19.45	230.65	166.52	11.68
1977-78	(10.59) 2.99	(89.41) 15.26	18.25	186.64	187.37	9.74
1978-79	(16.38) 3.87	(83.62) 17.97	21.84	231.61	219.28	9.96
1979-80	(17.72) 4.18	(82.28) 23.07	27.25	182.85	241.36	11.29
1980-81	(15.34) 3.05	(84.66) 22.31	25.36	203.80	259.84	9.76
1981-82	(12.02) 6.78 (24.91)	(87.98) 20.44 (75.09)	27.22	223.37	338.98	8.03
1982-83	3.85	32.15	36.00	251.29	422.04	8.53
1983-84	(10.69) 7.71 (28.29)	(89.31) 19.54 (71.71)	27.25	204.35	365.77	7.45

^a Figures in parentheses are percent of total bullock cost/ha.